

BASIC SUBSTANCE APPLICATIONS MANUAL

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

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Changes to this document

Version	Changes
3	Update to reflect the new format of IUCLID 6.8 and to make some editorial changes. Main changes relevant for the basic substance applications are in the: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Gap- SummaryEvaluation document- New paragraph on the extension of the application to support additional uses(s)
2	April 2022 Update to reflect the new functionalities of IUCLID 6.6
1	First version - August 2021

INTRODUCTION

This manual should be read in conjunction with the Working Document on the procedure for application of basic substances to be approved in compliance with Article 23 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009¹ (SANCO/10363/2012 rev.11, 12 July 2023; <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-08/pesticides-application-basic-substances-art-23.pdf>), and EFSA practical arrangements under the Transparency Regulation (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate-pubs/transparency-regulation-practical-arrangements>).

If you need support you should use the Ask a question web page: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applications/askaquestion>

Creating an application

Basic substance applications should be created in **IUCLID Cloud Services**: <https://ecs.echa.europa.eu/cloud/home.html>.

Before starting to compile a dossier it is recommended to check EFSA's Applicants Toolkit for the latest resources to support dossier preparation (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applications/toolkit>)

On this website you will find the link to [European Food Safety Authority. \(2021, May\). EFSA: IUCLID Training for applicants](#). On the training page you can download either a PDF or a movie explaining how to use IUCLID cloud services.

- 1) The first step is to create a **Legal Entity** for the organization which is submitting the application and to create **user accounts** for the people authoring the dossier. See the Overview of ECHA Cloud Services section of 'IUCLID Training for applicants', [Video 8](#) and the image below. More details on user management can be found in [ECHA accounts manual](#).
Important! A functional mailbox address and the number of a switchboard must be provided in the legal entity since this is always published whereas personal contact details should be included in the "Contact" entity.

Legal entity name*
EFSA IUCLID demo

Legal entity type
company

Remarks

Other names ⓘ ^ + New item ⓘ Imp

#	Flags
---	-------

Address ⓘ ⓘ

Address 1
Via Carlo Magno, 1A

Address 2

Postal code
43126

Town
Parma

Region / State

Country
Italy

Phone
+390521036111

Fax

Email
generic.company.email@mail.com

Web site
www.company.com

¹ Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC. OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 1–50.

- 2) The next step is to create a '**Mixture dataset**'² and select the '**EU PPP Basic substance application**' working context. See the Overview of IUCLID cloud services and Creating a dossier sections of '[IUCLID Training for applicants](#)'.

Note: Pay attention to the instructions for setting the confidentiality flag/s since a non-confidential version of the dossier will be made publicly available once the application is deemed 'valid for further evaluation'. The publicly available version of any attachments should not be in word/rtf format, but rather in pdf format.

Note: a substance dataset is not required for a Basic substance application

Note: there are no Endpoint Study Records in a Basic substance application

- 3) For a Basic substance application, A MIXTURE DATASET with the following IUCLID documents must be completed:
- The [dossier header](#) containing the administrative data and indicating the reason in case of a dossier resubmission
 - [Section 1](#) Identity and applicant, including the Legal entity and details for the contact person
 - [Section 2](#) Preparation of the substance for use, including a description of the composition of the preparation for use

² A mixture dataset is a collection of IUCLID documents/forms which are connected via a table of contents based on the data requirements of the application.

- [Section 3](#) Summary of intended uses, including one or more document/s describing each of the intended uses
- [Section 4](#) Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests, upload the Application template document

The relevant entities³ in the IUCLID documents must also be completed

- [literature reference](#)
- [reference substance](#)
- [legal entity](#)
- contact persons.

To add a document to a dataset, click on the red crosses next to the Section Labels.

Detailed instructions on completing the IUCLID documents and entities are provided in the sections below.

- 4) Before submitting a dossier, it is important to run the **validation assistant** to check the dossier is technically complete. The [rules](#) applied are dependent on the information included in the Dossier Header, make sure this is completed correctly.

If the report shows a **business rule failure** (anything starting with BR, e.g. BR_PPP_033) this will prevent the dossier from being successfully submitted.

If the report shows a **validation warning** (anything starting with QLT, e.g. QLT_PPP_001) the dossier can be submitted but might not pass the validity check. If you cannot resolve all the

³ IUCLID entities are documents which cover a specific topic e.g. contact details or substance identity. Entities are reused in other IUCLID documents to reduce typing the same information in multiple places. Entities can be managed in the Inventory Manager.

warnings re-run the validation assistant, download the excel file and include in this file the justification for not resolving the warning and provide this directly to the EC.

To run validation assistant click on the 'Validate' button at the top right hand corner of the dossier.

- 5) Once the dataset is complete you need to first create a dossier⁴ then submit it to EFSA via the 'Submission portal'. See the How to create a dossier section of 'IUCLID Training for applicants'

Once the dossier is created the message below will be shown. Click on the 'Proceed to submission' button and the dossier will be sent to EFSA via the Submission Portal.

 Dossier creation was completed successfully.

Extension of the application to support additional use(s)

The application for the extension of use should also be submitted electronically in IUCLID format. The applicant must provide evidence that the proposed extension of use meets all the approval criteria of Article 23 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009. The applicant can make use of the original application and the available EFSA Technical Report and must provide additional information as required to demonstrate that the substance is still compliant with the criteria for the additional uses. Additional information can be found in the working document on the procedure for application of basic substances to be approved in compliance with above mentioned Article 23 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, available here: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-08/pesticides-application-basic-substances-art-23.pdf>. For extension of uses, refer to chapter 2.3 of the above guidance and the information below:

Two cases of additional uses can be foreseen:

1. Additional uses are covered by the original uses (GAP) of the application: The risk assessment already performed for the uses included in the original application and presented in the already published Technical Report of EFSA can be easily extrapolated to the additional uses (i.e. the risk envelope approach can be applied). If the additional uses proposed are less or equally critical as the uses included in the original application (i.e. they are within the same "risk envelope", for further details see the Guidance document on the preparation and submission of dossiers for plant protection products according to the "risk envelope approach" SANCO/11244/2011), the applicant for extension of use does not have to provide additional

⁴ A dossier has the same content as a dataset but it cannot be edited.

data but shall provide the necessary rationale to demonstrate that the additional uses are covered by the original GAP.

2. Additional uses are not covered by the original GAP of the application: i.e. leading to potentially higher risk to humans, animals or the environment (e.g. uses where the supported application rates are higher). Applicants who want to support additional uses should compile the necessary data to support those uses and shall provide evidence that the proposed extension of uses meet all the approval criteria of Article 23 of Regulation 1107/2009 and submit them as part of an application.

Applicants should also consult the Commission Review Report containing the approved uses of the concerned substance which can be downloaded from the [EU Pesticide Database](#) from the EC website.

The application template available in Annex II to the Commission working document ([SANCO/10363/2012](#), rev. 11), should be completed and attached to the *FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation* document ([Section 4](#) – Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests).

For the points in which the applicant considers that the risk assessment already performed for the uses included in the approved application and presented in the already published Technical Report of EFSA can be extrapolated to the extension of uses, the applicant must provide substantiated justification with the necessary rationale to demonstrate that the additional uses are covered by the previous assessments and address the approval criteria for basic substances as laid down in Art 23 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009. This implies that sole reference to the EFSA Technical Report may not be sufficient without further elaboration, including adequate justification for the waiving as to why the applicant considers that the specific points are covered by the previous assessment and address the approval criteria for basic substances.

Also note that in case the application rate is higher than the already approved application rate (i.e. considered to be more worst case compared to the already approved GAP), this increase should be duly considered in the risk assessment.

With regard to the 'change log' section of the IUCLID dossier, indeed this should be compiled in case the applicant is using the dossier submitted for the initial basic substance approval, linking the IUCLID documents included in the dataset.

As a concrete example, in case in the *FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation* document in [Section 4](#) of the IUCLID dossier ('Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests'), the literature studies submitted under the basic substance approval, and also some new studies to support the application of extension of use as mentioned above are added, the change log document should be compiled linking the IUCLID document under section 4 (*FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation*) and the status should be set as 'updated'. See example in the screenshots below:

The left screenshot shows the 'change log' section of a dossier. It includes a search bar, a table of entries, and a 'Change log entries' section with options for 'New item' and 'Import file'.

#	Link to document	Status
1	Bibliography - Identity	updated
2		

The right screenshot shows the 'EU PPP Basic substance application' section. It includes a search bar and a list of items with 'Add new' buttons.

- 2 Preparation of the substance for use + Add new
 - Composition (mixture) 001
 - Composition (mixture) 002
- 3 Summary of intended uses + Add new
- 4 Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests + Add new
 - Bibliography - Identity
 - Bibliography - Mammalian toxicology
 - Bibliography - Residues
 - Basic Substance Application template
- 5 Change log + Add new
- 6 Additional transparency regulation information + Add new

Set values [X]

Link to document
Bibliography - Mammalian toxicology

Status [i] [^]
updated [X] [v]
press Esc to close

Remark

XYZ
24c0a235-2365-49d9-ba02-5767e0391ae2

View Dossiers [Validate]

Working context
EU PPP Basic substance application

Type at least 3 characters

- EU PPP Basic substance application
 - xyz
 - 1 Identity and applicant
 - 2 Preparation of the substance for use*
 - 3 Summary of intended uses
 - 4 Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests
 - Basic Substance Application template
 - Bibliography - Identity
 - Bibliography - Mammalian toxicology
 - Bibliography - Residues
 - 5 Change log
 - Change log.001

Change log.001
UUID: 56fbac64-6110-4334-9a95-aaba6768310b

General Information [Change log]

General Information [Summary]

Change log

Change log entries [New item] [Import file]

#	Link to document	Status	Remark
1	Bibliography - Identity	previously used	
2	Bibliography - Mammalian toxicology	updated	new studies included to support the application for extension of use

Links to supporting material:

<https://echa.europa.eu/support-echa-accounts-and-eu-login>

https://iuclid6.echa.europa.eu/documents/21812392/22308501/iuclid_functionalities_html_en.pdf/9d01cb53-902d-dbb6-fb00-fa141688c395

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/21721613/echa_accounts_en.pdf

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4JGsQUbGYqw>

Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID

All attachments should be provided in two versions. A sanitised version of any report included in the Literature reference entity or summary and evaluation section must be provided for the public consultation. It is important that all names, signatures and other personal data **are redacted** in the sanitised version. In parallel, an **earmarked version** of the document must be provided so that all details are available to the assessors and to facilitate the confidentiality check.

Important: If only personal data, for example an author or study director name, has been redacted from an attachment the CBI flag should not be set but the text box should be completed with the justification as described in the instructions provided in the User guide submission of confidentiality requests: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/user-guide-submission-confidentiality-requests.pdf>

For details on copyright rules please see section “[Literature Reference](#)” section of this manual.

EU PPP BASIC SUBSTANCE APPLICATION

DOSSIER HEADER

The dossier header contains administrative data and information about the type and purpose of the application. Information in the dossier header is used by IUCLID tools to process the dossier, for example different validation assistant scenarios could be applied depending of the selection of the purpose of the application. This information is also used in automated e-mail notifications.

Please note that all information in the dossier header is published by default. Confidential data should be provided elsewhere in the dossier as appropriate.

DOSSIER.EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE_APPLICATION		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Dossier template	Working context: select EU PPP basic substance application	Header 1
Dossier name (given by user)	Report short name for the dossier (this should be maintained in all versions). Refer to the basic substance name in the text (e.g. "Basic substance authorisation" or "Basic substance extension of uses authorisation"). Avoid additional information such as Company codes, company name and dossier versioning.	Text
Dossier subject		Block
Submitting legal entity	Select submitting legal entity	Link to entity
Dossier submission remark	Use this field to report useful additional information on the submission.	Text area
Basic substance approval		Header 1
European reference number	The European Reference Number (ERN) is the unique identifier used for linking all versions of a dossier submitted under a regulatory action. It can be generated within the IUCLID application (click on the 'cycle' button) and must NEVER be changed with subsequent submissions unless specifically requested to do so by EFSA.	Text
Scope of the application	Select either 'first application for the approval of a basic substance according to Article 23 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 Or 'extension of the application to support additional use(s)'	Closed list
Purpose of the application	Describe briefly the reasons to support the substance as basic substance and the envisaged uses in plant protection. Add when possible, information on its traditional use in agriculture (e.g. interest for organic agriculture).	Text
Contributors	Optional: Indicate the contributors to this application where organisations other than the submitting legal entity have contributed to the preparation of the dossier	Text
Specific submissions		Header
EFSA Question number	Enter the assigned EFSA question number in EFSA-Q-YYYY-NNNNN format (if available)	Text

The submission is an update	Indicate whether the submission is an update by selecting Yes or No	Picklist
Official request	Indicate the reason(s) for the update in the repeatable block. More than one reason can be provided	Header
Requester	Indicate which organisation has requested a resubmission - EFSA - EC - other:	Open list
Request type	Select the type of request - request for update during validity check - request for update linked to dossier publication - request for update following a request for clarification in the context of the confidentiality assessment process (after declaration of admissibility) - request for update during application evaluation - other:	Open list
Remarks		Text
Spontaneous update	Indicate the reason/s for the update in the repeatable block. More than one reason can be provided	Header
Reason for resubmission	Select the type of request - changes in administrative information - update following a legal entity change - new confidentiality claim(s) - new studies available - other:	Open list
Remarks		Text
Pre-application information		Header 1
Pre-application identification	Enter any pre submission identifiers issued whilst notifying studies for inclusion in regulated product dossiers relevant for this dossier subject, if applicable. https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-07/user-guide-notification-of-studies.pdf	
Pre-application identifier	Enter any pre-submission identifier issued whilst notifying studies in the EFSA notification of studies (NoS) system. If more than one pre-application Id is available, create a new entry in this section and list them separately.	Text
Studies requiring NoS justification	Click on the "red cross" to add information on studies requiring Notification of Studies (NoS) justification, if applicable.	
NoS ID	List all Notification of Studies identifiers (NoS ID) which are present in the database linked to the Pre-application identifiers (see above) and for which a justification is required according to EFSA's Practical arrangements.	Text
Justification	Justification for any procedural deviation from the obligations of study notification set out in EFSA's Practical arrangements	Multi-line text

Basic substance approval

European reference number*

46edfd4e-6bbd-44ee-9684-4c726b3849b2

Scope of the application*

first application for approval of a basic substance according to Article 23 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/200

Purpose of the application ⓘ ^

Basic substance application for use as insecticide in organic agriculture

73/32768

Contributors

Specific submissions

EFSA Question number

EFSA-Q-2021-00475

The submission is an update

yes

Official request

+ New item

📄 Import file ▾

1

Requester

EFSA

Request type

✓ request for update during validity check

Remarks

Spontaneous update

+ New item

📄 Import file ▾

Pre-application information

Pre-application identification

+ New item

📄 Import file ▾

Studies requiring NoS justification

+ New item

📄 Import file ▾

BASIC SUBSTANCE DATASET

This section includes instructions on how to compile the IUCLID documents in the basic substance dataset in line with the relevant changes released with IUCLID 6.8.

Mixture		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Mixture/Product name	This must be completed. Provide a name of a basic substance for which an approval is requested.	Multi-line text
Public name	Common name of the basic substance	Multi-line text
Legal entity owner	This must be completed and is always published; this information is also included in the dossier header as 'Submitting Legal Entity'. When submitting a dossier through the Submission Portal the same legal entity should be used, third party consultants may do this as foreign entities. Links the dossier to the Legal entity of the dossier owner.	Entity reference field
Third party	In case a third party prepares the dossier the legal entity of the third party can be added here	Entity reference field
Other identifiers		Header 1
	All former and current trade names and proposed trade names and development code numbers of the plant protection product/preparation shall be provided. Flags can be used to indicate if the trade name is confidential	
Confidential	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Name type	Select name type	Open list
Name	Provide name	Multi-line text
Country	Provide the country where the identifier is relevant.	Multi select open list
Remarks	Include remarks if relevant	Text area
Contact persons	Link to the relevant Contact entity . The primary contact point for the dossier should be provided, name, position, telephone and e-mail address. This information is not published by default.	
Person flags	This flag is not needed since the details on the Contact persons are not published by default.	Confidentiality
Person	See Legal Entity (including contact person)	Entity reference field

Role in the supply chain		Header 1
	Check 'Manufacturer' to indicate the applicant is the Producer of the plant protection product	

1. Identity and applicant

Purpose:

This document covers the data requirements:

- Applicant and contact person
- Trade name of a substance as available on the market

A screenshot of a web application's navigation menu. The menu is structured as follows:

- EU PPP Basic substance application (with a document icon)
- Substance A (with a downward arrow icon)
- 1 Identity and applicant (with a downward arrow icon and a '1' count)
- Substance A (highlighted in blue, with a downward arrow icon)
- EFSA IUCLID demo (with a building icon)
- Person, Example; Applicant company (with a person icon)

A screenshot of a data entry form for 'Substance A'. The form contains the following sections:

- Mixture/Product name***: Substance A
- Public name**
- Legal entity owner**: EFSA IUCLID demo | Parma | Italy
- Third party**
- Other identifiers**: Includes '+ New item' and 'Import file' buttons.
- Table of identifiers**: A table with columns '#', 'Confidential', and 'Name type'.
- Contact persons**: Includes '+ New item' and 'Import file' buttons.
- Contact person list**: A list with one entry:
 - 1 Person: Person, Example; Applicant company | Person | Example | Applicant company | Town | Italy

2. Preparation of the substance for use

Purpose:

This document covers:

- Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the plant protection product/preparation
- Product formulation type and function of component

In accordance with Art. 23 (1) (c) of the PPP Regulation basic substances should be useful in plant protection either directly or in a product consisting of the substance and a simple diluent. In some cases, the substance can be used as such. When the substance is not to be used directly, sufficient information should be provided for the mixture(s) which is (are) expected to be prepared by the users.

The preparation for use may be simply the same as a substance for which the approval is sought.

The preparation for use may be an undiluted or pre-diluted mono-constituent substance or plant extract. The linked [reference substances](#)⁵ should include main components, impurities etc.

CUSTOM_SECTION.EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE_COMPO		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see Confidentiality Requests Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID - practical instructions for applicants	Confidentiality
General information		Header 1
Mixture/ product name	Name of formulation/preparation reported. In case of multiple formulations more than one document can be completed. For example "preparation for use 1", "pre-dilution 1" etc	Text

⁵ A reference substance is an entity which provides details on the identity of a component in the preparation e.g CAS number or Chemical formula

Trade names		
Country		Multi select open list
Trade name	In case a preparation for use is available on the market in a ready-to-use form, indicate the relevant trade name(s), the name(s) of manufacturer(s) and (a) link(s) to the relevant website(s) (if available).	Multi-line text
Brief description	Enter a brief description of the mixture/product if appropriate.	Text
Formulation type	Select the formulation type according to the international coding system for pesticides from the scroll down list	Multi select open list
Components		Header 1
Component flag	See Confidentiality Requests Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID - practical instructions for applicants	Confidentiality
Name	Link to reference substance for all components If a component of the mixture is confidential it is important that the confidentiality flag of the reference substance entity is also set to CBI to ensure substance identifiers are not shown in the mixture composition document.	Entity reference field
Function	Indicate the function of the component in the formulation. For all mixture formulations in the dossier a single component with the function 'active substance' must be reported. The reference substance with the function 'active substance' must be the same for all mixture composition documents included in the dossier.	Open list
Typical concentration	Complete the Typical concentration reporting %w/w. For relevant impurities the range including the maximum content is required.	Half-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Concentration range		Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks	Describe in detail the recipe (or dilution process) for the preparation of the substance as it will have to be applied for use in plant protection. All the required transformation steps have to be thoroughly explained, as a sort of recipe for the preparation and/or the use. The recipe for the preparation of the substance for use will become an integral part of the specifications for the use of the basic substance and will be included in the Review Report.	Text area
Substance of concern	Not relevant for Basic substance. The approval as a basic substance is possible only if a substance is not a substance of concern (see Art 23 of the Regulation (EU) No 1107/2009).	Check box
Substance generated <i>in situ</i> (from one or more		Check box

precursors, at the place of use)		
---	--	--

Preparation of the substance for use_Substance A

UUID: 4ca1362c-7039-442b-b4c7-38213b16e832

Administrative data General information Components

Administrative data

General information

Mixture/product name
Substance A

Trade names + New item Import file ▾

Brief description
Decoction from foodstuff A

Formulation type
DC Dispersible concentrate

Components

+ New item Import file ▾

#	Component flag	Name	Function	Typical concentration	Concentration range	Remarks	Substance
1		Foodstuff extract Not available	active substance	30 % (w/w)		30 g of Substance A is added to 1 L of tap water in a glass vessel at room temperature and stirred with stainless steel spoon until complete dissolution. Following preparation, the resulting solution can be stored for up to 24h at temperature between 4°C and 20°C before use.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2		Water 7732-18-5	diluting agent	70 % (w/w)			<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Summary of intended uses

Purpose:

The IUCLID GAP form implements the following data requirements:

- Details of intended use
- Application rate
- Method of application
- Number and timing of applications and duration of protection
- Necessary waiting periods or other precautions to avoid phytotoxic effects on succeeding crops

If you click on the red plus sign next to the header 'Summary of the intended uses' you can create a new GAP.

Please note that separate GAP documents need to be created, if the GAPs differ in one or more of the parameters. For some fields multiple options from a picklist can be selected. Please read carefully below the instructions to see whether in a given case a separate GAP document needs to be created or whether it is appropriate to describe the different use options in one form.

- **EU PPP Basic substance application**
- ▼ **Substance A**
- > **1 Identity and applicant** 1
- > **2 Preparation of the substance for use*** 1
- ▼ **3 Summary of intended uses** 2
 - > **Summary of intended uses_Ornamentals**
 - > **Summary of intended uses_Pome fruits**

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.GAP		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Product	This field is mandatory. Click on the red plus sign to link the GAP to an existing Preparation (composition as reported in Section 2). If no preparation is available in the inventory, create first a new one	Endpoint reference field
Description of key information	The free text field can be used to give a short explanation/description of the GAP. This information is not mandatory. For GAPs that involve different application methods at different growth stages (e.g. drench application at sowing followed by foliar application at a later growth stage), the GAP should be split in separate GAPs (in the example the first GAP being the drench application, the second the foliar use). In this field, the GAPs belonging to a sequential application should be labelled (e.g. GAP 1 of 2, GAP 2 of 2).	Header 1
Purpose of the GAP		Header 2
Active substance / microorganism / basic substance applications	Select the term that describes the purpose of the GAP.	Multi select closed list

MRL applications	Not relevant for basic substances	Multi select closed list
Crop information		Header 2
Crop/treated object	<p>Information on the crop/treated object is mandatory. A picklist is implemented to describe the crop or object to be treated with the product.</p> <p>The picklist is based on EPPO codes which have been enhanced with additional information to make them more user friendly/self-explanatory. The extended EPPO codes cover the following types of information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the first 5 digits are the EPPO code (see EPPO Plant Protection Thesaurus at http://eppt.eppo.org) (e.g. PIBSX), • followed by the scientific name of the crop (PIBSX <i>Pisum sativum</i>); • in brackets, the crop name in English is reported (PIBSX <i>Pisum sativum</i> (English pea)); • for the most important crops, the corresponding food code of the MRL food classification is reported after a dash (code of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005). For some crops, more than one food code is applicable (e.g. PIBSX <i>Pisum sativum</i> (English pea) - 0260030, 0260040, 0300030). <p>In the current version of IUCLID, the link with the food codes of the MRL legislation has been established only for codes listed in Part A of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005; food codes listed in Part B of Annex I to, the connection to the crop code has not yet been implemented (the link will be included in the next release of IUCLID).</p> <p>Please note that not for all codes all four name elements are available.</p> <p>To find the codes for the crop/object, the user can either use the hierarchy search tool which requests to choose between crops or treated products.</p> <p>Alternatively, a text string (e.g. the EPPO code, the scientific name) can be directly entered in the search window, resulting in a subset of matching options.</p> <p>In the hierarchy tool, the user should first select between the two highest hierarchy levels 'crops' or 'treated product'. Treated products is relevant only for post-harvest uses and for uses on non-crop objects (e.g. treatment of railways).</p> <p>As a next step, a text string (EPPO code, scientific name, name of the crop in English or the food code of the MRL legislation) can be inserted. EPPO codes matching with the search term are displayed in yellow, and the user should select the relevant one.</p> <p>For post-harvest treatment of food products, two EPPO codes are available (HARFO and HARPO) which were combined with all food codes (Part A) of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005:</p>	Multi select open list with remarks

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the treatment with the product is intended on the fresh harvested product (e.g. oranges), the code combining HARFO and the respective food code should be selected (e.g. 3HARFO – Oranges – 011020). • For GAPs describing a use on a processed harvested product (e.g. raisins), the code HARPO in combination with the food code should be used (e.g. 3HARPO – Table grapes – 0151010). <p>In general, codes for crop groups should not be selected. Instead the EPPO codes for the individual crops should be chosen. A multiple selection of crop codes is allowed, only if all parameters of the GAP are identical for all crops selected. If the GAPs differ for the individual crops in one or several fields, a separate GAP form needs to be completed. To facilitate the work to complete separate GAP forms, an existing GAP can be copied and modified for the respective parameters.</p> <p>Further remarks on the crop/treated product can be reported in the associated free text field 'Remark'.</p> <p>Remarks are necessary to specify whether food or feed has been in contact with the plant protection product indirectly if one of the following codes for treated product has been selected:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>3IRRWO</td> <td>irrigation water (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>BULBO</td> <td>bulbs, tubers, corms (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PLABO</td> <td>plant base (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SEEDO</td> <td>seeds (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>WOUNO</td> <td>wounds (treatment of)</td> </tr> </table>	3IRRWO	irrigation water (treatment of)	BULBO	bulbs, tubers, corms (treatment of)	PLABO	plant base (treatment of)	SEEDO	seeds (treatment of)	WOUNO	wounds (treatment of)	
3IRRWO	irrigation water (treatment of)											
BULBO	bulbs, tubers, corms (treatment of)											
PLABO	plant base (treatment of)											
SEEDO	seeds (treatment of)											
WOUNO	wounds (treatment of)											
Genetical modification of crop	If relevant, describe variety of genetically modified crops on which the use of the product is intended to be used or authorised.	Closed list with remarks										
Crop destination(s)	<p>The field is not mandatory.</p> <p>Please select the relevant EPPO code for crop destination. Multiple selection is allowed (e.g. grown for animal consumption (3ANICD) and grown for human consumption (3HCOND)).</p> <p>In remarks field more details on the crop destination can be described. See also EPPO code list https://gd.eppo.int/PPPUse/3CRODK</p>	Multi select open list with remarks										
Authorisation zone	Not relevant for Basic Substances	Closed list										
MRL zone	Not relevant for Basic Substances	Closed list										
Country or territory	Select the country or the territory related to the GAP. The selection of more than one country is possible if the same GAP applies.	Multi select open list										
Crop location (F/G/I)	This data element is mandatory for GAPs that refer to crops (children codes listed under crops and children codes of '3HARVO harvested crops (treatment of)'. For other GAPs the field should remain empty.	Multi select closed list with remarks										

	<p>The available picklist contains EPPO codes with detailed descriptions of the cases.</p> <p>I: Code to be used for crops grown or stored in closed walk-in buildings. This code includes for example mushroom houses and structures for witloof chicory or rhubarb forcing.</p> <p>G: A walk-in, static, closed place of crops production with a usually translucent outer shell, which allows controlled exchange of material and energy with the surroundings and prevents release of products into the environment.</p> <p>F: Fields and other structures which do not prevent release of products into the environment.</p> <p>For crops grown outdoor (F), more details can be reported using the more specific subcodes. The detailed description of the subcodes is provided in the picklist.</p>	
<u>Pest/disease to be treated</u>		Header 1
Target organisms	Select 'New item' and compile the block consisting of 'Scientific name', 'Common name', 'Development stage of target pest' and 'Development stage of target plant'. See detailed descriptions below.	
Scientific name	<p>Select the appropriate code and scientific name from picklist. The picklist is based on the EPPO list (https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/).</p> <p>At least one target organism needs to be defined in a GAP. It is possible to select more than one target organism, if the GAP parameters are identical for the different target organisms.</p> <p>If the target organism is not listed, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>If a scientific name is not relevant or not known, select 'no data'.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for target organism if required according to a programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses, e.g. 'I.1.1.1 (EU BPD)'.</p> <p>Please make sure that the scientific name entered in this field matches with the organism described in the field 'Common name'.</p>	Open list with remarks
Common name	Please add the common name of the target organism in this field that matches with the Scientific name.	Text
Development stage of target pest	<p>For insecticide and fungicide uses, indicate the developmental stage of the target organism/pest (e.g. development stage of the insect or of the disease for diseases caused by fungi).</p> <p>If no appropriate description is available in the list, select 'other:' and specify the development stage in the remarks.</p> <p>If the development stage is not known or not further specified, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If the development stage is not relevant/applicable, leave field empty.</p> <p>Multiple selection of terms is allowed.</p>	Multi select open list with remarks

<p>Development stage of target plant</p>	<p>For herbicide uses, indicate the developmental stage of the target plant. In the picklist BBCH codes have been implemented. Although these codes have been developed for describing the development stages of crops, they can be used in analogy for the target plants. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance an alternative description of the developmental stage which is not available in the picklist.</p>	<p>Multi select open list with remarks</p>																								
<p>Major/minor use</p>	<p>Not relevant for Basic Substances</p>	<p>Closed list with remarks</p>																								
<p>Application details</p>																										
<p>Application target</p>	<p>The target to be treated can be selected from a picklist. The following terms are implemented:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="450 806 1139 2049"> <thead> <tr> <th>Picklist value</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Foliage/Plant</td> <td>Application to a plant or the leaves of a plant.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Seed / Seed Pieces</td> <td>Application to a small object produced by a plant from which a new plant can grow.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Propagation Stock</td> <td>Application to a specimens of a plant, used for breeding by natural processes from the parent stock.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Root/Bulb</td> <td>Applications (such as dip applications) to a rootball (the compact mass of roots), or bulb (a part of plants that functions as a food storage during dormancy).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Bark</td> <td>Application to or into the tough, protective outer sheath of the trunk, branches, and twigs of a tree or woody shrub.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Stump / cut stem</td> <td>Application to the recently cut of a tree or woody shrub (excludes cut flowers).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Containerized plant</td> <td>Application to a plant and soil grown in a movable container.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agricultural Commodity</td> <td>Post-harvest application to an agricultural product that can be bought and sold (<i>e.g.</i>, treatment to grain, fibre, cut flowers, packaged animal feed, <i>etc.</i>).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Soil (surface)</td> <td>Application to the ground in which plants can grow.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Soil (subsurface)</td> <td>Application below the ground, or immediately incorporated.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Water</td> <td>Application to water in systems, pools, pipes, tanks or other containers, or bodies of water, such as lakes, ponds, bays, estuaries, oceans, reservoirs.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Picklist value	Description	Foliage/Plant	Application to a plant or the leaves of a plant.	Seed / Seed Pieces	Application to a small object produced by a plant from which a new plant can grow.	Propagation Stock	Application to a specimens of a plant, used for breeding by natural processes from the parent stock.	Root/Bulb	Applications (such as dip applications) to a rootball (the compact mass of roots), or bulb (a part of plants that functions as a food storage during dormancy).	Bark	Application to or into the tough, protective outer sheath of the trunk, branches, and twigs of a tree or woody shrub.	Stump / cut stem	Application to the recently cut of a tree or woody shrub (excludes cut flowers).	Containerized plant	Application to a plant and soil grown in a movable container.	Agricultural Commodity	Post-harvest application to an agricultural product that can be bought and sold (<i>e.g.</i> , treatment to grain, fibre, cut flowers, packaged animal feed, <i>etc.</i>).	Soil (surface)	Application to the ground in which plants can grow.	Soil (subsurface)	Application below the ground, or immediately incorporated.	Water	Application to water in systems, pools, pipes, tanks or other containers, or bodies of water, such as lakes, ponds, bays, estuaries, oceans, reservoirs.	<p>Header 2</p>
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	Air	Application directed to a space, rather than a specific target. Examples of these types of applications include foggers, mosquitocides, ozone generators, knock-down insecticides, etc. This does not include aerial broadcast applications over a crop because the target is the crop, not the air over the crop.	
	Surface	Application to the interior and/or exterior boundaries of an inanimate object. Examples of these types of applications include boat hulls, countertops, hives, nests, etc.	
	Non-porous Surface	Surfaces where liquids will not absorb such as ceramic, porcelain, glass, metal, plastic/vinyl, rubber, stainless steel.	
	Porous Surface	Surfaces where a liquid is likely to absorb such as fabric, drywall, composition board surfaces, paint films and surfaces, plaster surfaces, and wood.	
	other		
Method of application	<p>Please select the most appropriate treatment target.</p> <p>Information on the application method is mandatory. Select the treatment/application method relevant for the GAP. The picklist is based on the EPPO list (https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/).</p> <p>If no EPPO code is available to describe the method of application, select 'other:' from the picklist and describe the method of application in the remarks. Examples for methods of application with no EPPO codes are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bait treatment - basal bark treatment - dabbing/rubbing - [local treatment] - incorporation into compost - material incorporation or impregnation - [no class] - paint - [local treatment] - paste guns for volatile substances - pressure treatment - prune/wound treatment - [local treatment] - soil bed solarization <p>The remarks field can be also used to provide further details on the EPPO code selected to describe the method of application.</p>		Open list with remarks

	<p>Examples for further specification of some EPPO codes are listed below:</p> <p>Circulating water application (3CWATM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hydroponic/aquaponic water treatment <p>Fogging (3FOGGM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mechanical fogging - thermal fogging <p>Fumigating (3FUMIM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fumigation: enclosed spaces - fumigation: vacuum chamber - gassing <p>Injecting (3INJEM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stem injection <p>Placing (3PLACM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - doseable matrix dispensers for volatile substances - retrievable active dispensers for volatile substances - retrievable passive dispensers for volatile substances - non retrievable active dispensers for volatile substances - non retrievable passive dispensers for volatile substances <p>Spraying (3SPRYM):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - air assisted broadcast spraying - high volume spraying - low volume spraying - ultra low volume spraying - application in overhead irrigation water - banded spraying - spot treatment (spraying) <p>Spreading (3SPRDM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - granules application in row - granules application overall <p>If different application methods are foreseen on a crop (e.g. seed treatment followed by foliar broadcast), two uses should be described as separate GAPs, including in the remarks that the two GAPs are combined.</p>	
<p>Application equipment</p>	<p>Select the types of application equipment used. This information is used in the operator and worker exposure scenarios</p>	<p>Multi select open list with remarks</p>
<p>Growth stage and season</p>	<p>Click on 'New item' and compile the block of fields that comprises the following fields:</p> <p>Growth stage of crop (first application), Growth stage of crop (last application), Treatment season.</p>	

	<p>If the GAP foresees treatments at different treatment windows (e.g. first treatment window before flowering, second treatment window after flowering), the block can be repeated.</p> <p>Information on the growth stage is mandatory if the GAP refers to a crop; if the GAP refers to treatment of non-crop objects (children of 3NOCFO), it is not required; if the GAP refers to treatment of harvested crops (children codes of 3HARVO), BBCH 99 should be entered; if the GAP refers to children codes of 3CRPAO (treatment of crop parts), it is not required.</p> <p>If number of applications is greater than 1, the information on the growth stage needs to be reported for the first and the last application. Treatment season is not mandatory.</p>	
Growth stage of crop (first application)	<p>This field is intended to describe the growth stage of the crop at the first treatment with the product. The picklist offers the BBCH codes which describe the phenomenologically similar growth stages of all mono- and dicotyledonous plant species (source: BBCH Monograph edited by Uwe Meier, Julius Kühn-Institut, 2018, https://www.julius-kuehn.de/media/Veroeffentlichungen/bbch%20epaper%20en/page.pdf).</p> <p>Select the growth stage of the crop at first application. If a treatment is foreseen at one specified growth stage, select the BBCH code only in this field (Growth stage of crop (first application)).</p> <p>For a range, also select the relevant BBCH code in the field 'Growth stage of crop (last application)'.</p> <p>If necessary, more details on the treatment timing shall be reported in remarks (e.g. a description of the timing/growth stage at the application to specify more detailed the timing of the application (e.g. pre-plant, before transplant, etc.).</p> <p>The letters in bracket after the description of the crop development show to which plant group the respective definition refers. (D = Dicotyledons, M = Monocotyledons, G = Gramineae, P = Perennial plants, V = Development from vegetative parts or propagated organs).</p> <p>Please note that BBCH codes 71 to 79 is not used, if the main fruit growth happens in principal growth stage 8.</p>	Open list with remarks
Growth stage of crop (last application)	<p>Please select from the picklist the growth stage of crop at last application. See above (Growth stage of crop (first application)) for further details.</p>	Open list with remarks
Treatment season	<p>For autumn/winter sown crops, report whether the treatment is foreseen in autumn/winter or in spring/summer. Multiple selection is allowed. If necessary, any other restrictions for the treatment season can be reported in the remarks field, selecting the option 'other:'</p>	Multi select open list with remarks
Number of applications (range)	<p>Information on the number of applications is mandatory. Report the number of applications (e.g. 1 – 3) <u>per crop cycle</u>.</p>	Precise range (Decimal)

	If only one treatment is foreseen, report '1' in the lower numeric field.	
Re-treatment interval (in days)	Enter the interval between treatments (re-treatment interval); if relevant, a range for minimum interval and maximum interval between treatments, expressed in days, can be reported.	Precise range (Decimal)
Application rate per treatment (product) – range	<p>Mandatory information. For reporting the application rate, follow the recommendations on dose expression for products (EPPO General Standard PPI/239(3)).</p> <p>Enter the numeric value in the first numeric field corresponding the lower application rate (for the formulation) per treatment.</p> <p>Use the second numeric field to report the upper application rate per treatment. Select the most appropriate unit to express the application rate.</p> <p>For applications on crops, the application rate should preferably be expressed as application rate per hectare.</p> <p>See also below application rate per treatment for target a.s. (range).</p>	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks on application rate	<p>Any further explanations related to the application rate can be provided in this field.</p> <p>For 3-dimensional crops, the application rate expressed on leaf wall area can be reported in addition to the application rate reported per hectare.</p>	Text
Water amount per treatment / spray volume	For products applied after dilution with water, the minimum and maximum amount of water used in spray application (spray volume) should be reported.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Concentration of target a.s. in dilution	For products applied after dilution with water, report the concentration of the active substance in the diluted solution.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Concentration of formulation in dilution	For products applied after dilution with water, report the concentration of the formulation in the solution.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Safener/ synergist/ adjuvant added	Not relevant for Basic Substances	Closed list with remarks
Application rate per treatment for target a.s. (range)	<p>It is mandatory to report the application rate for the target a.s.</p> <p>The field is intended to specify the application rate for the target active substance (i.e. the a.s. defined in the active substance dataset (EU PPP Active substance information) of the IUCLID dossier).</p> <p>For reporting the application rate, follow the recommendations on dose expression for products (EPPO General Standard PPI/239(3)).</p> <p>Enter the numeric value in the first numeric field corresponding the lower application rate per treatment.</p> <p>Use the second numeric field to report the upper application rate per treatment.</p>	Range with open list (Decimal)

	<p>If the formulation contains a variant of the active substance (e.g. an ester), the application rate should be expressed for the a.s. (not for the variant!).</p> <p>Example for a variant: the formulation contains quizalofop-P-terfuryl which is a variant of the a.s quizalofop-P. In the field defining the application rate for the target a.s. the application rate should be expressed as quizalofop-P. The factor to recalculate the application rate of quizalofop-P-terfuryl (molecular weight 428.9) to quizalofop-P (molecular weight 344.7) is derived as the ratio of the molecular weight ($344.7/428.9=0.804$).</p>	
Maximum annual application rate (a.s.)	If restrictions need to be defined for the annual application rate (in case of crops which have more than one harvest per season), please report the maximum annual application rate for the active substance. The application rate should be reported for the a.s. (not the variant).	-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Non-target a.s.		FLEXIBLE_RECORD.GAP.PestDiseaseTreated.ApplicationDetails.NonTargetAS
Non-target a.s.	Not relevant for Basic Substances	Entity reference field
Application rate per treatment for other a.s. (range)	Not relevant for Basic Substances	Range with open list (Decimal)
Maximum annual application rate for other a.s.	Not relevant for Basic Substances	Half-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Concentration of other a.s. in dilution	Not relevant for Basic Substances	Range with open list (Decimal)
Treatment window (for dispensers)	For dispensers or similar application forms, the duration of treatment window needs to be reported.	Text
Seeding rate	<p>Field relevant for seed treatments only.</p> <p>Enter the seeding rate: For crops where the seeds are usually sold by number of units (e.g. sugar beet, maize, sunflower), the seeding rate should be expressed as unit/ha (unit is usually 100.000 individual kernel). For seeds sold by weight (e.g. cereals the seeding rate is normally expressed in kg or g seeds /ha or m²).</p> <p>If 'other:' is selected as unit, describe the seeding rate unit in the additional field.</p>	Half-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Planting density	<p>The field is not mandatory.</p> <p>Describe the planting density (number of plants per ha or m²).</p>	Text
Pre-harvest interval not applicable	The checkbox should be ticked if the PHI is 'Not Applicable' e.g. cases where the pesticide is applied to empty storage rooms, or for treatment of fields after harvest. In case 'not	Check box

	applicable' is selected, further clarifications should be provided in the 'Remark' field.	
Remarks	Provide any further clarifications as needed	
Minimum pre-harvest interval (in days)	Specify the minimum pre-harvest interval (PHI) in days (i.e. the minimum time between the last treatment of a crop and the harvest). This field should also be used to describe the time between post-harvest treatment of a food/feed item and the placement on the market. Enter a single numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Re-entry period livestock	The field is not mandatory. This field should be used to describe the minimum re-entry period (hours/days) for livestock, i.e. the time that needs to elapse before animals may enter treated pastures.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Withholding period animal feed	The field is not mandatory. This field is intended to define the minimum time (in days) between harvest of a feed crop and the use of the feed.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Re-entry period	The field is not mandatory. Describe the minimum re-entry period (in days or hours) for workers in the field/room treated with pesticide, in order to safeguard human health. If no re-entry period is defined/required, select 'not applicable'.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Waiting period handling treated product	The field is not mandatory. This field is intended to describe the minimum waiting periods (hours/days) that need to be respected between treatment and handling of treated products (e.g. handling of products after fumigation).	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Ventilation practices	The field is not mandatory. If relevant, please describe the ventilation practices to be carried out after indoor treatments, to safeguard human health.	Multi-line text
Plant-back interval	The field is not mandatory. If relevant, please describe the plant-back interval (expressed as days) that has to be respected (e.g. in case of crop failure) before the planting of succeeding crops is allowed.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Restrictions	The field is not mandatory. If relevant, please report any relevant restrictions that would have an impact on the risk assessment e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - geographical restrictions, - restriction related to use of other a.s., - maximum number of applications per season for a.s. belonging to the same group (e.g. dithiocarbamates, triazoles), - restrictions for rotational crops, - PPE, - buffer zones, - temperature range at application, - soil incorporation depth and time, - restricted soil type, - restriction to crops grown in artificial substrate, 	Multi-line text

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - restriction to be used only in crops grown in hydroponic systems, - restriction to crops grown in pots/no connection to natural soil, - restrictions to be used in crops up to a certain crop height, - minimum percent soil organic matter, - restrictions to protect pollinators, - restriction regarding application equipment. 	
Type of user	<p>The field is not mandatory.</p> <p>Please select one or several terms from the picklist (professional/non-professional/other:). If other is selected, please provide more details in the remark field.</p>	Multi select open list with remarks
Additional information	Any relevant information on the GAP that cannot be reported in any of the data fields above should be entered in this field.	Header 1

Good agricultural practices (GAP).001
 UUID: 110e9484-b6f1-4a5a-bbd7-71c1ccaf792c

Administrative data | Description of key information | Pest / disease to be treated | Additional information

Administrative data

Product
 Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the plant protection product.001

Description of key information

Crop information
 Crop / treated object
 1ZANG Zanthoxylum - 0820020 (crops > 1ZANG Zanthoxylum - 0820020)
 3ALLC (Allium vegetable crops) (crops > 3ALLC (Allium vegetable crops))
 Genetical modification of crop

Crop destination(s)
 Crop location (F/G/I)

Pest / disease to be treated

Target organisms + New item | Import file

	Scientific name	Common name	Development stage of target pest	Development stage of target plant
1	other: Altemaria Solani			

Application details
 Application target
 bark [application to or into the tough, protective outer sheath of the trunk.]
 Method of application

4. Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests

Purpose:

Summarise the overall conclusions for the basic substance.

The completed Application template and literature references should be included in this document.

Important note: To facilitate the risk assessment and ensure data are easily accessible, a FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation document should be created **for each value** of the 'Complementary Information' field (see below), organising the **bibliography** or **supporting documentation** into sections (e.g. uses of the substance, impact on human and animal health, effects on non-target organisms).

Furthermore, in order to facilitate the literature data search, we recommend using an **appropriate numbering** and **naming convention** when renaming the FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation documents as per the example in the picture below.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation_EU_PPP		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	See administrative data	Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see Confidentiality Requests Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID - practical instructions for applicants	Confidentiality
Complementary information	Use this field to select the type of bibliography or supporting documentation reported in this document.	

	<p>Note: A FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation document should be created for each value of the this field, organising the bibliography or supporting documentation into sections (e.g. uses of the substance, impact on human and animal health, effects on non-target organisms).</p>	
Reports and administrative information	Filled in application template has to be uploaded.	Header 1
Reports and administrative information		
Type of report	<p>Indicate the type of document that has been uploaded e.g. 'Application template'.</p> <p>If the FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation document is used to submit bibliography for a specific section, this field could be left empty as no attachments are expected.</p>	Multi-line text
Attached confidential document	<p>Upload the completed Application template. In this document if any information is claimed confidential then it must be boxed or earmarked.</p> <p><u>Only DOC(x) or PDF formats are allowed for file upload.</u></p> <p>The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions.</p> <p>If a file is uploaded under this field, (a) confidentiality request(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.</p>	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) document for publication	<p>Upload a sanitised version of the Application template with confidential information blackened.</p> <p><u>Note: if there is no confidential material it is sufficient to just upload the Application template in Attached (sanitised) document for publication</u></p> <p><u>Only PDF format is allowed for file upload.</u></p> <p>Any document uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.</p>	Single file attachment

Reports and administrative information		
Other references (including SDS)	<p>The literature reference entity should be completed for each literature reference and test study report relied upon in the application.</p> <p>All literature references can then be included in the dossier in the 'Other references (including SDS)' section.</p> <p>Simply click on select to add each of the literature reference entities.</p> <p>Each literature reference has to be uploaded individually, in a non-compressed format (please note that uploading content in a .zip or .rar file is not allowed).</p> <p>Note: Only literature references supporting the section selected in the field "complementary information" should be linked.</p> <p>A separate FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation document should be created for each section of the application (see instructions above).</p>	Header 1
References		Literature reference list
Additional information		Header 1
Additional information	Overall summary of the main conclusions for the substance or mixture can be entered here	Rich text area

Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests.001
 UUID: 2a1db7b9-a869-4001-ab87-35a834d704a2
 CBI EU: PPP

Administrative data | Reports and administrative information | Other references (including SDS) | Additional information

Administrative data

[Complementary information](#)
identity of the substance

Reports and administrative information

[Reports and administrative information](#) New item Import file

Type of report	Attached document	Attached (sanitised) document for publication
Other references (including SDS)		
References ^		
other company data Study		
Select		

5. Change log

Purpose:

This document can be completed if the scope of the application is 'extension of the application to support additional use(s)'

The document allows the differentiation between 'New' and 'Previously used' documents. More information on the extension of the application to support additional use(s) is provided in the dedicated paragraph [above](#).

	EU PPP Basic substance application	
▼	Substance A	
>	1 Identity and applicant	1
>	2 Preparation of the substance for use*	1
>	3 Summary of intended uses	2
>	4 Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests	1
▼	5 Change log	1
>	Change log	

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.ChangeLog		
Name	Instructions	Data type
General information		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see Confidentiality Requests Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID - practical instructions for applicants	Confidentiality
Summary	Provide any additional explanation needed in order to facilitate the compilation of the final list of the tests and studies relied upon and whether the study was already submitted in the first approval.	Rich text area
Change log		Header 1
Change log entries	Create an entry in the table for each test or study	
Link to document	Select each of the IUCLID documents included in the dataset	Endpoint reference field
Status	For each of the documents indicate if the document is 'new', 'previously used' 'obsolete' or 'updated'	Closed list
Remark	In the remark indicate for which data point the study has been previously used	Multi-line text
Change log entries		

REFERENCED ENTITIES

Reference substance

Purpose:

Chemicals: Identity of the substance – ISO common name and synonyms, Chemical name in accordance with IUPAC and CA nomenclature, CAS Reg number, EC number, molecular and structural formula, molar mass.

The Reference substance inventory gives the possibility to use the same information for the same chemical/microorganism identity avoiding duplicate data entry and to ensure that the data is centrally managed and updated. Each reference substance can be linked to an unlimited number of substance or mixture datasets.

Reference substance/s can be exported and shared from the Reference substance entity manager.

REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE		
Name	Instructions	Type
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see Confidentiality Requests Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID - practical instructions for applicants Important: Setting this flag ensures that substance identity is not published in any IUCLID document where a link to the reference substance is used. This should be used for confidential substances included mixture or substance composition documents	Confidentiality
Reference substance name	Name of substance, microorganism, metabolite, residue, impurity or other substance included in the dossier For the active substances the ISO common name or proposed ISO name should be reported	Multi-line text
IUPAC name	IUPAC name (Note that, if a name following the IUPAC nomenclature cannot be derived, you should still provide a name defining the chemical nature of the substance).	Multi-line text
Description	Specify any additional information relevant for the description of the reference substance in this field	Text template
Inventory	Can be used to select existing substances with pre-assigned EC numbers.	Header 1
Inventory number	Can be used to select existing substances with pre-assigned EC numbers.	Entity reference list
No inventory information available - Justification	Not relevant for Basic Substance	Open list with remarks
CAS number	CAS Registry Number	Text

CAS name	CAS name	Multi-line text
CIPAC number	CIPAC number	
Synonyms		Header 1
Synonyms	List any synonyms for the substance EFSA paramCode should be added in the table	
	Set confidentiality and regulatory program flags	Confidentiality
Identifier	Select the type of identifier you wish to provide using the picklist. If none of pre-defined items apply, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can specify the type of identifier you wish to provide.	Open list
Identity	Enter here the identity (name, number, code) corresponding to the identifier type selected.	Text area
Remarks		Text
Synonyms	Synonyms	
Molecular and structural information	Molecular and structural information	Header 1
		Confidentiality
Molecular formula	Molecular formula (if a molecular formula cannot be derived from the reference substance, a justification should be indicated in the Remarks field at the bottom of the section)	Multi-line text
Molecular weight	Molecular weight should be reported as a single numeric value	Range (Decimal)
SMILES notation	The SMILES notation should be in the canonical form https://cactus.nci.nih.gov or generated by ChemSketch or ChemDraw	Multi-line text
InChI	The IUPAC international chemical identifier https://cactus.nci.nih.gov or generated by ChemSketch or ChemDraw	Multi-line text
Structural formula	The structural formula for the active substance https://chem.nlm.nih.gov/chemidplus/structure3D/viewer/ ChemSketch, ChemDraw	Image
Remarks	See molecular formula	Text area
Chemical structure files	Upload chemical structures files (both machine readable and an image file) For machine readable files the format should be .sk2 or .cdx or .mol For image files the format should be jpg or png	
Structure file		Single file attachment

Remarks on structure file		Text
Chemical structure files		
Related substances	Not relevant for Basic Substance	Header 1
Identifier	Not relevant for Basic Substance	Open list
Identity	Not relevant for Basic Substance	Text area
Remarks	Not relevant for Basic Substance	Text
Relation	Not relevant for Basic Substance	Open list
Group / category information	Not relevant for Basic Substance	Multi-line text

Literature reference

Purpose

Storage of bibliographic metadata with attached documents including full study reports and published scientific papers

Linking studies to the Notification of Studies Database

Used as the data source in OECD harmonised templates and DOMAIN Endpoint Study Records.

It is important to create a Literature reference for all studies used as evidence in the dossier. This would also include all relevant studies selected for full-text assessment identified from a literature search (when required).

Additional considerations

The applicant must ensure that terms and conditions asserted by any rightsholder of studies, information or data submitted to EFSA are fully satisfied. The applicant may consult with copyright licensing authorities (i.e. at national level) for guidance on purchasing the appropriate licenses to provide studies, information or data to EFSA, taking into account the proactive disclosure requirements as detailed in the relevant section of this manual. For publications already available to the public upon payment of fees (e.g. studies published in scientific journals) for which the applicant does not have or cannot obtain IPRs for the purposes of the proactive public disclosure requirements, the applicant must provide (a) a copy of the relevant publications along with the relevant bibliographic references/ citations for scientific assessment purposes only, in the confidential version of its application and (b) these relevant bibliographic references/citations where these publications are available to the public in the non-confidential version of its application for public dissemination on the OpenEFSA portal.

LITERATURE		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
General information		Header 1
Reference Type	Select 'study report' for a full study report used as a data source for an endpoint study record. Select 'published' for relevant studies identified from a literature search to address data requirements	Open list

	<p>Select 'other company data' to characterise any unpublished information from a company other than a study report.</p> <p>For any other select 'other:' and specify.</p> <p>Only in case of a publication already available to the public (studies published in scientific journals or similar publications) but subject to access restrictions (e.g. upon payment of a fee) for which the applicant does not have or cannot obtain IPRs for the purposes of the proactive public disclosure requirements, select 'publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)'</p>	
Title	Title of the study report, publication or other report type	Text
Author	Author names for the study. These will be redacted from the published dossier for unpublished toxicology studies.	Multi-line text
Year	The year the report must be reported (this is used for sorting and filtering)	Integer
Bibliographic source	For published studies information on the journal and edition should be completed. This should include the DOI (Digital Object Identifier)	Text
Testing facility	For study reports information on the testing facility should be completed. This information will not be published for studies involving tests on vertebrate animals.	Text
Report date	Report date or publication date in full. For study reports this must be after the date the study was notified in the notification of studies database	Date
Report number	Specify the report number allocated by the testing laboratory. This information will not be published for studies involving tests on vertebrate animals.	Text
Study sponsor	Information on the source of funding of the study can be provided	Text
Study number	Report the company identifier, if it differs from the laboratory report number	Text
Other study identifier(s)	<p>Applies to study reports.</p> <p>When other study identifiers are available e.g. NoS number, click on 'New item' and compile relevant fields accordingly.</p>	
Study ID type	Select 'Notification of studies (NoS) ID' when reporting a NoS ID or studies carried out or commissioned after 27 March 2021 for which the study notification requirement applies.	Open list
Study ID	Report the relevant identification number retrieved from the Notification of Study system.	Text
Remarks	If the study was not notified provide a justification to explain why the study is included in the dossier to meet the data requirements but was not included in the Notification of Studies database. Example 'Study commissioned before 27 March 2021'.	Text area

Other study identifier(s)		
Attachments		
Attachment type	<p>Select 'full study report' to identify the original study report. Only one set of attachments (original and sanitised) can be set to 'full study report'.</p> <p>Use 'other' to indicate the type of content of the other sets of attachments e.g. addendum</p>	Open list
Attached confidential document	<p>The applicant has selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType":</p> <p>a copy of the relevant publication in PDF format along with the relevant bibliographic references/ citations needs to be provided for scientific assessment purposes only. The uploaded attachment will not be included in published dossier but the citation will be published.</p> <p>The applicant has not selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType":</p> <p>The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field, (a) confidentiality claim(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential via the related endpoint record and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.</p>	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) document for publication	<p>The applicant has selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType":</p> <p>Only a citation including the abstract of the relevant publication should be uploaded in this field. The uploaded attachment will be included in the published dossier.</p> <p>The applicant has not selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType":</p> <p>any document uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if</p>	Single file attachment

	<p>applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.</p> <p>Other supporting documentation e.g. addendum can be uploaded.</p>	
Attachments		
Remarks	<p>Additional remarks on the uploaded literature reference content can be added here.</p> <p>Note: if an applicant provides a sanitised/public attachment which contains personal data (and this is not an issue because the document is already publicly available), this should be mentioned in the Remarks field to avoid misunderstanding.</p>	Text

General information

Reference Type
publication

Title* ? ^ ? ^
 Example 2 publication about Substance A

Author
Author

Year
2023

Bibliographic source
Bibliographic source

Testing facility

Report date

Report number

Study sponsor

Study number

Other study identifier(s) + New item 📁 Import file ▼

#	Study ID type	Study ID	Remarks	Actions

Attachments + New item 📁 Import file ▼

#	Attachment type	Attached confiden...	Attached (sanitise...	Actions
1	other: Publication		Author_2023.pdf	

Links to supporting material

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/stakeholders/transparency-regulation-implementation>

Legal entity (including contact entity)

Purpose:

Submissions require a Legal entity which has to be defined including contact details prior to submission. A Legal Entity (LE) may represent anything between a complex business structure and a small business enterprise, for example, a corporation, a company, or a single person. LEs are identified by their name, universally unique identifier (UUID), address, country, and general contact information. You can create a Legal Entity Object (LEO) via [ECHA accounts](#)

A legal entity should identify in an unambiguous manner a company or organisation with a role in the submission of dossiers. The submissions attributed to a specific company/applicant should all have the same legal entity. The same applies to third party consultants, they should also maintain a unique legal entity that can be included in the 'Third Party' field.

The information provided in the Legal entity should be similar to that provided in a publicly accessible company register. It should contain the address and contact details, including fax and phone number as well as e-mail address, of the legal person. The information provided in the Legal Entity is always published. Hence, no personal information relating to natural persons should be provided under these fields. **Do not include personal e-mail addresses and telephone numbers!**

Note that the information regarding the Contact person is to be managed in the Contact entity manager. The information provided in the Contact entity is by default not published.

You can add more legal entities within the IUCLID application via the inventory.

LEGAL_ENTITY		
Field name	Instructions	Data type
General information		Tab
Legal Entity name	Name of the legal entity i.e. Company name	Text
Legal entity type	Select one legal entity type from the dropdown menu. If other, please include an explanation in the free text field below.	List (picklist)
Remarks	Any additional information on the legal entity, if relevant	Text
Other names	Other names can be specified and if needed these names can be marked as confidential	Block of fields (repeatable)
Address	See Confidentiality Requests	
Address 1	Street address of the legal entity	Header 1
Address 2	Secondary address, if relevant	Confidentiality
Postal Code	Postal code of the legal entity	Text
Town	Town of the legal entity	Text
Region/State	Region/State of the legal entity	Text
Country	Select the country in which the legal entity is located from the dropdown menu. If other, enter the appropriate country information in the free text field below.	Text
Phone	Phone number of the legal entity (this field must not contain personal data, therefore e.g. the number of a switchboard should be provided)	Text
Fax	Fax number of the legal entity (this field must not contain personal data)	Text

Email	Email address of the legal entity (this field must not contain personal data, therefore e.g. the email address of a functional mailbox should be provided)	Text
Web site	Legal entity website	Text
Identifiers	Optional: Other identifiers can be reported. Legal entity identifiers, Regulatory programme identifiers, and Other IT system identifiers. Each type contains a menu from which relevant sub-types of identifier can be selected. For example, Legal entity has an option for DUNS (Data Universal Numbering System for identification of a Legal Entity). Click on New Item and set values. See Confidentiality Requests.	Tab
Contact information	An address can be defined for a contact person of the Legal entity and links can be made to one or more Contact entities	Tab
Contact Person	This can be managed in the Contact entity manager	
General information		Header 1
Contact type	Select one contact type from the dropdown menu. If other, enter the appropriate contact type in the free text field below.	Open list
Last name	Last name of the contact person. Note that this field is mandatory	Text
First name	First name of the contact person.	Text
Organisation	Name of the Organisation. Note that this field is mandatory	Text
Department	e.g. Scientific Department	Text
Title	Title of the contact person (e.g. Mr.).	Text
Phone	Phone number of the contact person	Text
Mobile	Mobile phone number of the contact person	Text
Fax	Fax number of the contact person	Text
Email	Email address of the contact person	Text
Address 1	Street address of the contact person	Text
Address 2	Secondary address, if relevant	Text
Postal Code	Postal code of the street address of the contact person	Text
Town	Town of the contact person	Text
Region/State	Region/State of the contact person	Text
Country	Select the country in which the contact person is located from the dropdown menu. If other, enter the appropriate country information in the free text field below.	Open list
Remarks	Any additional information, if relevant	Text area

VALIDATION ASSISTANT RULES

The currently applicable Validation Assistant rules in IUCLID as well as those applicable to the Submission portal are available in [Zenodo](#).

FILTERING RULES

IUCLID filtering rules for PPP dossiers currently applicable are available in a separate document at the following link: [IUCLID for PPP Filter rules | Zenodo](#)